

The Impact Of Cognitive And Affective Perception Of The Country Image On Consumers' Sense Of Economic Animosity, Product Quality Judgment, And Purchase Intention¹

Bilişsel ve Duygusal Ülke İmajı Algısının Tüketicilerin Ekonomik Düşmanlık Hissi, Ürün Kalite Yargısı ve Satın Alma Niyeti Üzerindeki Etkisi

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Abstract

In a globalized world, the image of countries has increasingly become an important factor influencing consumers' product preferences. In this context, studies that examine the effects of cognitive and emotional country image perceptions on economic animosity, product quality judgment, and purchase intention have gained prominence in the marketing field. The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of Turkish consumers' cognitive and emotional country image perceptions of U.S.-origin products on their feelings of economic animosity, product quality judgments, and purchase intentions. The research was conducted among consumers aged 18 and above in Istanbul using a convenience sampling method. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) were employed, and reliability and validity were assessed through Composite Reliability (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Cronbach's alpha. Descriptive statistics and correlation analyses were also performed to explore the relationships between variables, ensuring methodological rigor. The analysis results indicated that emotional country image components (admiration and contempt) had a significant impact on economic animosity, while cognitive com-

ponents (competence and warmth) did not. Additionally, the perception of competence regarding the people of the country positively influenced beliefs about the products; however, the emotional image did not affect product judgment. In terms of purchase intention, competence from the cognitive image and contempt from the emotional image were influential, and both economic animosity and product judgment were found to impact purchase intention.

Keywords Country of Origin Image, Consumer Animosity, Product Quality Judgment, Purchase Intention.

JEL Codes: M30,M31

Özet

Küreselleşen dünyada, tüketicilerin ürün tercihlerine etki eden unsurlar arasında ülkelerin imajı giderek önem kazanmaktadır. Bu bağlamda, bilişsel ve duygusal ülke imajı algısının ekonomik düşmanlık hissi, ürün kalite yargısı ve satın alma niyeti üzerindeki etkilerini inceleyen araştırmalar pazarlama alanında öne çıkmaktadır. Bu çalışmanın amacı, Türk tüketicilerin ABD menşeli ürünlere yönelik bilişsel ve duygu-

¹ The compliance of this study with ethical guidelines was approved by the Ethics Committee of Atatürk University with decision number 231, dated December 10, 2021.

sal ülke imajı algılarının, ekonomik düşmanlık hissi, ürün kalite yargısı ve satın alma niyetleri üzerindeki etkilerini incelemektir. Kolayda örneklem yöntemi ile İstanbul ilinde 18 yaş üstü tüketiciler üzerinde gerçekleştirilen araştırmada, Doğrulamalı Faktör Analizi (DFA) ve Yapısal Eşitlik Modeli (YEM) kullanılmış, güvenilirlik ve geçerlilik Bileşik Güvenilirlik (CR), Ortalama Varyans Açıklaması (AVE) ve Cronbach alfa ile değerlendirilmiştir. Değişkenler arasındaki ilişkileri keşfetmek için betimleyici istatistikler ve korelasyon analizleri de gerçekleştirilmiştir, bu sayede çalışmanın metodolojik titizliği sağlanmıştır. Yapılan analizler sonucunda, duygusal ülke imajı bileşenlerinin (hayranlık ve küçümseme) ekonomik düşmanlık üzerinde anlamlı bir etkisi olduğu, ancak bilişsel bileşenlerin (yeterlilik ve samimiyet) bu his üzerinde etkili olmadığı belirlenmiştir. Ayrıca, ülkenin insanlarına dair yeterlilik algısının ürün inançlarını pozitif etkilediği; fakat duygusal imajın ürün yargısı üzerinde etkisi olmadığı saptanmıştır. Satın alma niyetinde ise bilişsel imajdan yeterlilik ve duygusal imajdan küçümsemenin etkili olduğu, ayrıca ekonomik düşmanlık ve ürün yargısının da niyeti etkilediği görülmüştür.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Menşé Ülke imajı, Tüketici Düşmanlığı, Ürün Kalite Yargısı, Satın Alma Niyeti.

JEL Kodları: M30,M31

Introduction

Türkiye, The increasing prevalence of globalization and the expansion of free trade have elevated the significance of foreign markets. These developments have spurred the growth of international trade relations, fueling consumer demand for products from diverse countries. Consequently, there is a pressing need to comprehensively analyze the factors that influence consumers' willingness to purchase goods from different nations and to conduct further research in this area (Klein et al., 1998, p. 89; Riefler & Diamantopoulos, 2007, p. 88). Literature overview reveals that previous research on country of origin has established its role as an external prompt influencing consumer choices between identical products from different countries (Bilkey & Nes, 1982, p. 89; Verlegh, 2001, p. 523; Nart, 2008, p. 155; Dmitrovic & Vida, 2010, p. 146). Current research has shifted its emphasis to exploring the factors that influence consumer preferences for products from specific countries. This perspective suggests that a good reputation of a country's products can only be justified when considering the production of particular goods. Roth and Diamantopoulos (2009) introduced the notion of country image (COI), which refers to the perceptions and evaluations held by consumers in one country towards another. COI is a causal factor in a country's affairs and comprises two interconnected components: cognitive and affective (Roth & Diamantopoulos, 2009, pp. 726-728). The intellectual component relates to the expression of beliefs,

while the affective component pertains to consumer actions towards further country. The formation of country image is influenced by various factors, including the dissemination of information through media channels and the significance of family and peer networks in providing insights into foreign countries and cultures (Maher & Carter, 2011, pp. 560).

Although the significance of the concept of country image is well acknowledged, there is no universally agreed-upon definition or measurement approach in academic literature (Roth & Diamantopoulos, 2009, p. 726). However, empirical research suggests that emotional and cognitive factors differentially impact consumer purchasing behavior. Emotional dimensions influence preferences for hedonic goods, while cognitive dimensions drive preferences for functional items (Verlegh, 2001, p. 523; Maher & Carter, 2011, p. 560). Attitudes are shaped by both emotional responses and cognitive evaluations of attributes. These evaluations are often perceived as rational and logical. However, attitudes may vary in their responsiveness to affective and cognitive influences. For instance, household goods, with their instrumental nature, may be evaluated more on utilitarian grounds than emotional ones. Conversely, Lavine et al. (1998) argue that attitudes towards close friends or relatives are primarily driven by emotions rather than beliefs. Prior research (Lavine et al., 1998, p. 402; Maher & Carter, 2011, p. 560) suggests that when affect and cognition are misaligned, the affective dimension tends to exert a stronger influence on behavior. However, when both affect and cognition are congruent, they appear to have comparable impact on attitudes and behaviors. The hypothesis of the superiority of the senses in determining preferences was proposed by Zajonc (1984). Affective responses can often be chronologically preceded by cognitive reactions in shaping of attitudes (Edwards and Von Hippel, 1995: 998). When we meet a person for the first time, we may have a sudden affection-based reaction before we know anything about his or her personal characteristics. Nevertheless, affectional responses are more subjective than cognitive ones and are directly about the individual. For this reason, when two types of information contradict each other, the affections created by an attitude reveal more real assessments than our cognitive assessments of the attributes of the object (Edwards and von Hippel, 1995, p. 998; Lavine et al., 1998, p. 402).

The perception of perceptual and emotional image of country image can significantly influence consumer behavior, particularly in areas like economic animosity, product quality judgment, and purchase intention. Consumers with a negative affective response towards a country may still recognize the level of its products but are less likely to purchase them due to feelings of animosity. This interplay between emotional responses, cognitive assessments, and buying decisions highlights the complex

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relationship between country image and consumer behavior, with economic and emotional factors playing a significant role in guiding purchase intentions. According to the BIAS map, while the cognitive component consists of two dimensions (warmth and competence), while the affective component includes four dimensions: admiration, contempt, envy, and pity (Maher and Carter, 2011, p. 566). In this study, the dimensions of envy and pity were not included due to their weak relationship with behavioral tendencies.

The BIAS map extends the stereotype content model The Stereotype Content Model (SCM) (Cuddy et al. 2007, p. 632; Cuddy et al. 2008, p. 70). SCM suggests that individuals, as members of one group, judge another group based on their perceived warmth and competence. While the warmth dimension shows that other group individuals are positive towards their group intentions, the competence dimension shows another group's ability (Maher and Carter, 2011, p. 565). According to SCM, the origins of perceived frankness and competence lie in social structural variables, namely competition and status. Close people are considered warm. In contrast, those seen as competitors are considered to lack warmth. Also, while people who have been seen as having high status are thought of as competent, people who have been seen as having lower standing are thought of as ineligible (Cuddy et al. 2008, p. 64).

Various studies have examined the relationship among the emotional and cognitive angles of a country's image. While some research suggests that cognition precedes emotion (Brijs, et. al, 2011), others argue that emotion can influence cognition (Haubl, 1996; Maher & Carter, 2011). There is ongoing debate about whether affect and cognition are independent systems and whether affect can occur without prior cognitive processing. Zajonc's (1984; 2004) work on the interplay between cognition and affect is relevant here. He argues that there is no inherent connection between the two and that emotions can arise before perceptual and cognitive decoding. Given this perspective, our study has treated cognition and emotion as separate constructs. The following can be used to summarize these contributions:

- Foreign consumers' perceptions of a nation's goods and services are shaped by its image. Customers can learn valuable information from this image about the dependability and quality of products. A thorough examination of the emotional and cognitive aspects of national image will provide a better understanding of how it influences consumer purchase decisions.
- While cognitive components (competence and warmth) include more reasoned and informed evaluations, emotional components (admiration and contempt) reflect the impulsive feelings consumers

feel toward a nation and its products. An examination of the way these two elements interact will yield crucial information about how marketing strategies ought to be developed.

- Customers who harbor economic animosity are those who have unfavorable feelings about the prosperity of other nations. Gaining an understanding of how this emotion influences opinions about products and plans to buy will offer strategic insights that help direct brand positioning in global marketplaces.
- Brands may better meet the wants and expectations of their customers by having a deeper understanding of the psychological and sociocultural elements that affect consumers' decision-making processes. As a result, marketing and communication strategies can be created that are more successful.
- It is crucial for businesses that operate in international marketplaces to comprehend how consumers behave in various cultural contexts. We will be able to create effective plans and gain a deeper understanding of consumer trends in various markets thanks to this research.

This study examines the distinct dimensions of the cognitive and emotive components associated with the image of a country, specifically focusing on warmth, competence, admiration and contempt. Furthermore, this study will provide managers with the opportunity to recognize the significance of emotion and cognition as influential factors in their evaluation of the country's image.

The study looks at how consumers' behavior is influenced by their emotional and cognitive perceptions of their nation. This demonstrates that consumers have emotional as well as knowledgeable opinions about various nations and goods. Additionally, it offers a thorough explanation of how animosity influences customer behavior, including intent to buy and judgments about the quality of products. The study compares Turkish consumers' impressions of the US and Turkey in order to adjust for cultural variations. These distinctions will make it possible for businesses doing business internationally to include cultural considerations when formulating their marketing plans. Additionally, recommendations for marketers' and practitioners' practical application will be derived from the findings.

Theoretical Background

In the increasingly interconnected global marketplace, consumers' purchasing decisions are remarkably shaped by their perceptions of a product's country of origin. Under these circumstances, country image significantly influences consumer behavior. However, existing research lacks comprehensive studies that fully explore the combined effects of cognitive

and emotional country image perceptions on consumers' economic animosity, product quality assessments, and purchase intentions. The goal of this study is to bridge this gap by enhancing the literature on how country image affects consumer behavior.

Country of Origin Image

Generally considered a country of origin concept, the phrase "made in" indicates the place where a product is manufactured (Papadopoulos, 1993, p. 4; Liefeld, 2004, p. 86; Amine, 2008, p. 405). Country of origin image (COI) is defined as "the sum of people's beliefs, ideas, and impressions about a particular country" (Cotîrlea, 2015, p. 166). This image positions countries in consumers' minds much like brands are positioned. However, unlike brand images that are often shaped through targeted marketing efforts, COI is not directly controlled by marketers (Papadopoulos & Heslop, 2002, p. 295). According to Kunzick (1997), COI formation is a complex communication process influenced by various information sources, including marketing communications, personal experiences with foreign cultures, and their subsequent reflections (Cotîrlea, 2015, p. 166).

The scope of a concept delineates what falls within its definition and what lies outside. Examining the descriptive areas in current country of origin image (COI) surveys reveals three distinct focal points: (1) general country image, encompassing the overall perceptions and associations related to a country; (2) product-country image, referring to the image of a specific product category linked to a particular country; and (3) product image within a country, which focuses on the image of an individual product within the context of its country of origin (Roth & Diamantopoulos, 2009, p. 727). COI can significantly influence consumer behavior, as products from countries perceived to have high standards of craftsmanship, technology, or innovation are often viewed more favorably. On the other hand, products from countries with negative associations may face skepticism or avoidance.

Recent research has revealed a hierarchy of effects associated with country of origin (COO), highlighting a correlation between COO effects and a country's degree of economic progress. Consumers in industrialized nations often exhibit a preference for domestically produced goods over foreign ones, while those in developing nations tend to perceive foreign products as more valuable (Nagashima, 1970; Han & Terpstra, 1988, p. 236; Kotler et al., 2005, p. 352). This preference for foreign goods in developing countries may be attributed to perceptions of lower quality associated with domestically produced goods. The hierarchy of effects can vary by country (Han & Terpstra, 1988, p. 236), and attitudes towards COO can shift over time. The enhancement of the quality image of Japanese products exemplifies how

such perceptions can evolve (Kotler et al., 2005, p. 352; Verlegh, 2001, p. 525). Cuervo-Cazurra, A., and Ramamurti, R. (2022), meta-analysis examines the antecedents and outcomes of consumers' perceptions of foreign country images. It investigates how macro-level differences between countries moderate the effects of cognitive and affective dimensions on consumer behavior, particularly focusing on purchase intentions and economic animosity. De Nisco, A., and Oduro, S. (2022) explores the partitioned effects of country-of-origin on consumer behavior. It highlights how cognitive and affective perceptions of a country's image influence perceived quality and purchase intentions differently, offering insights into how companies can leverage these perceptions in marketing strategies. Purwanto, E., and Wibisono, A. (2020) focuses on the impact of country-of-origin image and word-of-mouth on perceived quality and purchase intention, particularly in the context of Japanese digital cameras. Structural Equation Modeling is used to test the hypotheses, revealing significant effects of country image on consumer decisions.

The Concept of Consumer Animosity

Consumer animosity refers to the lingering resentment arising from past or ongoing military, political, economic, or diplomatic conflicts between nations (Klein et al., 1998, p. 90; Klein, 2002, p. 346). This deep-seated negative sentiment toward a specific country significantly influences consumer behavior in international markets (Klein et al., 1998, p. 90; Ettenson & Klein, 2005, p. 204). Unlike consumer ethnocentrism, which generally reflects a preference for domestic over foreign products, animosity is directed at a particular country and shapes preferences among foreign products (Klein et al., 1998, p. 90; Klein & Ettenson, 1999; Klein, 2002, p. 346). Consumer animosity can stem from war, trade disputes, political disagreements, or human rights violations, and may persist even after the original source of tension has dissipated. As a result, brands from countries facing consumer animosity may struggle to penetrate certain markets, requiring strategic efforts to mitigate these negative associations through localized marketing, brand repositioning, or even corporate social responsibility initiatives.

Various factors can contribute to negative attitudes toward a foreign country and its products (Ang et al., 2004, p. 192), including historical military conflicts, economic or diplomatic disputes, competition, religious, ethnic, or cultural differences, or perceptions that a country is harming one's home nation (Klein et al., 1998, p. 90; Amine, 2008, p. 408; Rose et al., 2009, p. 331; Richardson, 2012, p. 13). While consumers may not always exhibit ethnocentric behavior and may believe products should be judged on quality alone, they can still reject goods from a particular

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country due to animosity rooted in historical events, such as wars, or ongoing issues like economic embargoes (Ang et al., 2004, p. 192). This animosity often manifests as a refusal to purchase products from the target country (Nijssen & Douglas, 2004, p. 25; Nakos & Hajidimitriou, 2007, p. 57).

Balabanis and Diamantopoulos (2021) investigate how consumer animosity interacts with country image to influence purchase decisions. Their study examines the effect of economic animosity on consumer behavior and suggests strategies for companies to mitigate negative perceptions. Klein et al. (1998) conducted the first study on consumer animosity, developing a model to explain how such animosity impacts the purchase of foreign products. Their research, which focused on Chinese consumers' attitudes toward Japan and Japanese-made products, demonstrated that animosity toward a foreign country negatively affects the intention to purchase its products, regardless of perceived quality (Klein et al., 1998, pp. 89–91).

Most studies on consumer animosity have examined the attitudes of individuals from one country toward the products of another (Rose et al., 2009, p. 330). For instance, Jewish consumers have historically avoided German-made products, while New Zealanders and Australians have boycotted French goods in response to France's nuclear tests in the South Pacific (Klein et al., 1998, p. 90). Contrary to the current literature on purchasing products of foreign origin, they have designed that country origin will affect the consumer's purchasing decision independently of product judgment (Riefler and Diamantopoulos, 2007, p. 88). Although consumers' perceptions of product quality obtained from the country of origin information are positive, countries with problems associated with economic, political, and even military events may refrain from buying their products (Shin, 2001, p. 2; Richardson, 2012, p. 14).

The concept has been classified in various ways from the past to the present. First, Klein (1998) has classified it in two ways: war and economic animosity. While military situations in history cause war animosity, economic animosity is caused by such things as competition, unfair trade practices, the unreliability of trading partners, economic coercion, or economic attacks by foreign countries (Klein, 1998, p. 91; Nijssen and Douglas, 2004, p. 27; Riefler and Diamantopoulos, 2007, p. 99).

Nakos, G. E., and Hajidimitriou, Y. A. (2007) study the impact of national animosity on consumer purchases, focusing on the moderating role of personal characteristics. It discusses how consumer traits can influence the relationship between animosity and purchasing decisions. Jiménez and San Martín (2021) explore the role of country-of-origin image, ethnocentrism, and animosity in fostering consumer trust. They emphasize the moderating effect of fami-

liarity on these relationships, suggesting that consumer experience with a country can mitigate negative perceptions.

In consumer animosity research, scholars have aimed to understand how animosity influences product judgments and the willingness of consumers in hostile countries to purchase goods from the target nation. Numerous studies have focused on animosity toward a single country (Bahae and Pisani, 2009; Ettenson and Klein, 2005; Nijssen and Douglas, 2004; Shin, 2001; Witkowski, 2000; Klein and Ettenson, 1999; Klein et al., 1998). Most of this research has examined purchase intentions for foreign products (Nakos and Hajidimitriou, 2007; Edwards et al., 2007; Shoham et al., 2006; Hinck, 2005; Ettenson and Klein, 2005; Klein, 2002; Shin, 2001; Klein et al., 1998), consistently finding that animosity directly and negatively impacts the intention to buy products from the offending country. This hostility often stems from factors such as economic competition, political disputes, or historical conflicts, leading consumers to form negative attitudes toward that nation's products.

In past studies, economic animosity has been given more importance and place than war and political animosity studies (Riefler and Diamantopoulos, 2007, p. 99). Economic affairs are observed more often than war-based ones. For this reason, scientists have directed their studies to the study of the effects of economic events on purchasing behavior (Sutikno and Cheng, 2010: 5). The results of the study conducted on economic animosity have determined that economic animosity is an essential factor affecting the purchasing decisions of the target country's products (Nijssen and Douglas, 2004, p. 27). Therefore, we also take into account the international trade relations of countries with each other, and in our study, we incorporate the concept of economic animosity, one of the types of consumer animosity, into the scope of the research.

Product Quality Judgment

Country image refers to consumers' overall perception of the quality of products produced in a specific country. These perceptions can vary significantly across different countries (Bilkey & Nes, 1982, p. 89; Verlegh, 2001, p. 523). Notably, quality perception is often specific to product categories (Han, 1989), with the influence of country of origin varying based on the type of product. Some countries have built strong reputations in particular product categories due to specialization and expertise (Kotler et al., 2005, p. 352). A positive perception of quality can lead to repeat purchases and word-of-mouth promotion, while poor quality judgments may result in brand avoidance or negative reviews. Additionally, marketing efforts aimed at communicating product quality, through advertising, packaging, and certifi-

cations, can shape consumer perceptions and ultimately influence their buying behavior.

Consumers frequently utilize country of origin information, in addition to brand information, as a means to simplify the cognitive process of information processing (Chao and Gupta, 1995, p. 49). Consumers engage in the process of inferring product quality by utilizing a range of information cues or stimuli, which can be categorized as either internal (such as product performance) or external (such as brand name or product origin) indicators of product attributes (Bilkey and Nes, 1982, p. 89; Nart, 2008, p. 155; Dmitrovic and Vida, 2010, p. 150).

The examination of a product's country of origin (COO) can serve as a potential indicator of product quality and influence evaluations of products from that country (Han, 1989, p. 222; Martin & Eroglu, 1993, p. 193). This influence extends to consumer purchasing decisions and their perceived risk and value associated with the product (Roth & Diamantopoulos, 2009, p. 726). The halo effect, where consumers benefit from a country's overall image when evaluating product quality before purchasing, plays a significant role. Consequently, the perception of a nation indirectly impacts consumer attitudes toward a brand through inferential associations. Han (1989, p. 223) suggests that as consumers become more familiar with products from a particular country, the country's image becomes instrumental in shaping their perceptions of those products and, in turn, their attitudes towards the associated brands. This phenomenon can be considered a summary function of the country's image.

Johansson et al. (1985) shows that a country's image influences consumers' assessments of product characteristics but does not affect overall product evaluations. These findings support the 'halo effect' of a country's image in product evaluation (Bilkey, 1993, p. 101). Consistent with the literature on consumer animosity, it has been observed that Chinese consumers are less likely to purchase Japanese products or products made in Japan due to feelings of animosity. However, the research also revealed that animosity is independent of quality judgments; even if consumers harbor resentment, they still perceive Japanese products as high quality. Despite this, those who feel animosity are less likely to buy the products (Ferrín et al., 2015, p. 75; Klein et al., 1998, pp. 89–90).

Purchase Intention

Understanding how the behavior of individuals is shaped has been a subject of curiosity in many disciplines, such as social psychology and marketing. One of the most critical issues affecting behavior is the attitude of people towards objects. High purchase intention indicates a stronger probability that

the consumer will proceed to make the actual purchase (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975).

Various consumer behavior models can decipher the relationship between attitude and behavior. The most well-known theory about how attitudes predict behavior is the "Theory of Planned Behavior" (Aronson et al. 2012, p. 395). Ajzen (1991) established a hypothesis rooted in social psychology, positing that behavior is influenced by purpose. As to the aforementioned idea, the primary determinant of individual behavior is the individual's intention to engage in or abstain from the specific action under consideration. Ajzen (2005) posits that intention can be understood as an evaluation of an individual's level of motivation. This denotes the extent to which an individual is inclined to engage in a particular behavior. The buying intention is contingent upon the purchase process. According to Carter (2009, p 5), the purchasing process encompasses four distinct stages, including consumer assessment, attitude formation, purchase intention, and the actual purchase itself. It is one of the primary inputs that marketing managers use to predict future sales and assess how their marketing activities will influence consumer purchasing behavior (Morwitz, 2012, p. 182).

The Purpose of The Study Importance and Scope

The study aims to examine the impact of the cognitive and affective components of a country's image on consumer animosity, product quality judgments, and purchase intentions. The cognitive component reflects consumers' "beliefs," while the affective component represents their "feelings" about the people and products of a country. Animosity, which has psychological, emotional, and behavioral dimensions, is treated in the literature as a concept with multifaceted effects. Given the intensity of economic relations, the study focuses on analyzing Turkish consumers' cognitive and affective perceptions of the U.S. image, their feelings of animosity, and the influence of these factors on their judgments of product quality and purchase intentions.

There are many studies about the image of the country of origin in the literature. However, the number of studies investigating the effects of the cognitive and emotional dimensions of country image on consumer decisions is very small. This study decodes an interdisciplinary study that draws on social psychology and marketing literature. In contrast to studies that prioritize cognitive and affective components, this is one of the few studies in which the concepts of cognition and affection are considered independently. The findings to be obtained by examining concepts that are important in terms of international marketing activities, such as consumer animosity and country image, will guide practitio-

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ners. The study's limitation is that the research scope comprises young people living in Istanbul.

Based on the above conclusions it is possible to classify the purpose and importance of this study as follows:

1-) Advance Theoretical Understanding: Advance the theoretical framework of country image research by offering a deeper insight into the interaction between cognitive and affective dimensions and their distinct impacts on consumer behavior.

2-) Inform Business Strategies: Offer practical implications for businesses operating in the global marketplace. By understanding how country image perceptions influence consumer attitudes and behaviors, companies can tailor their marketing and branding strategies to mitigate negative perceptions and enhance product appeal.

3-) Empower Consumers: Enhance consumer awareness of the influence of country image on their purchasing decisions. By understanding the factors that shape their perceptions and preferences, consumers can make more informed choices and engage in critical consumption practices.

In conclusion, this study holds significant theoretical and practical implications for academics, businesses, policymakers, and consumers alike.

Methodology

Model and Hypothesis of the Study

The study model and hypotheses prepared according to the purpose of the research are shown below. The theory of social identity suggests that people tend to distinguish their own groups (e.g., their own countries) positively. A nation's reputation as a dependable and well-respected actor on the international scene can be enhanced by its citizens' high level of competence, which lessens economic animosity (H1). Perception of temperate has a role in fostering confidence in interpersonal relationships. By fostering a sense of familiarity and confidence in contacts with other nations, the perception of a country's people as kind and amiable helps lessen economic animosity (H2). Admiration conveys gratitude and pleasant feelings. By enhancing favorable sentiments toward a nation, admiration for its people can lessen economic animosity (H3). By reducing negative feelings toward a country and the feelings of contempt toward its people, this can also reduce the feelings of economic animosity toward that country (H4). Technological and manufacturing capacities are among the characteristics that are linked to the perception of competence. This impression may support the conclusion that the output is of a high caliber (H5). Warmth is typically linked to closeness and well-meaning intentions. This perspective

may give the idea that goods are made with the wants of customers in mind and with a high level of customer satisfaction in mind (H6). A nation's products can gain credibility via admiration for its people, which enhances the perception of product quality (H7). Contempt frequently has a negative impact on one's assessment of the quality of a product, but a more thorough examination of how this perception is processed is necessary to identify a positive influence in this hypothesis (H8). It forecasts how consumers' intentions to purchase goods from a given nation may be influenced by the emotional and cognitive aspects of that nation's image. Customers' inclination to purchase goods from that nation may be boosted by a high sense of competence, a favorable sense of warmth and admiration, and a low sense of contempt (H9-10-11-12). The feeling of economic animosity can result in a negative attitude towards the products of the hostile country and can cause reluctance to purchase the products of that country. In this respect, it negatively affects the purchase intention (H13). It asserts that consumers' perceptions of a product's quality can influence their inclination to purchase it. This is predicated on the notion that companies can boost consumer purchase intentions by highlighting the quality of their products (H14).

Figure 1. Proposed Research Model

H1: The perceived competence of the citizens of a country has a negatively impact on the feeling of economic animosity towards that country.

H2: The perceived warmth of the citizens of a country negatively affects the feeling of economic animosity towards that country.

H3: Admiration for the citizens of a country negatively affects the feeling of economic animosity towards that country.

H4: The feeling of contempt for the citizens of a country positively affects the feeling of economic animosity towards that country.

H5: The perceived competence of a country's citizens positively affects that country's product quality judgment.

H6: The perceived warmth of a country's citizens positively affects that country's product quality judgment.

H7: Admiration for a country's citizens positively affects that country's product quality judgment.

H8: The feeling of contempt towards a country's citizens negatively affects that country's product quality judgment.

H9: The perceived competence of the citizens of a country positively affects their purchase intention the products of that country.

H10: The perceived warmth of the citizens of a country positively affects their purchase intention the products of that country.

H11: Admiration for the citizens of a country positively affects the purchase intention the products of that country.

H12: The feeling of contempt towards the citizens of a country negatively affects the purchase intention the products of that country.

H13: The feeling of economic animosity negatively affects the purchase intention.

H14: Product quality judgment is positively affects the purchase intention.

The Scale of The Study

To measure the cognitive and affective dimensions of the country image included in the model, Maher and Carter (2011) used various studies (Cuddy et al., 2007) to compile and use 22 expressed scales.

The 5-expression scale developed by Klein (1998) has been used to measure economic animosity. In the measurement of product judgment (6 expressions) and purchase intention (6 expressions), scales compiled from Klein's (1998) (Wood and Darling, 1993; Darling and Wood, 1990; Darling and Arnold, 1988) studies have been used.

Sampling Process

The central mass of the research consists of consumers residing in Istanbul. Istanbul is Turkey's largest city and the most populous region. Therefore, consumers living in Istanbul may represent a large proportion of the general consumer mass in Turkey. The population aged 18 years and over has been considered the sample size. A easy sampling method has been used as a sampling method. A total of 421 questionnaires have been applied, and 376 questionnaires have been evaluated due to the elimination of incomplete and incorrectly completed questionnaires.

Data Collection And Methodology Tool

The research data were collected using a survey method. The questionnaire consists of two parts. In

the first part, 39 statements measure the variables of the research, using a 9-point Likert-type scale to assess the country's image (Cuddy et al., 2007; Maher et al., 2010). To gauge consumers' feelings toward the American people, respondents were asked to rate statements on a scale of 1 to 9. For measuring economic animosity, product quality judgments, and purchase intention, a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree) was used. The second part aims to determine the demographic characteristics of the respondents. It has four questions consisting of gender, age, marital status, and education status.

Validity And Reliability Analyses

Using the AMOS 20 program, a first-order confirmatory factor analysis was conducted on the general country image scale to test the scale's structural validity. Single-factor verification factor analysis was performed for other scales. Since the compliance values produced by the measurement models created for factor analysis are not within acceptable limits, notifications have been made to the scales based on the modification indices recommended by the AMOS program. The changes made in scale due to the modification are shown in Table 1. Table 2 displays the compliance values that the models produced.

Table 1. Changes to Scale

Scales	Dimensions	Number of Expressions	Number of Expressions Extracted
Country Image Scale	Competence	6	2
	Warmth	6	3
	Admiration	5	1
	Contempt	5	--
Economic Animosity Scale		5	--
Product Quality Judgment Scale		6	1
Purchase Intention Scale		6	1

As can be seen in Table 1, as a result of the modifications, a total of eight expressions were taken from the scales: two from the competence dimension of the general country image scale, three from the warmth dimension, one from the admiration dimension, one from the product judgment scale, and one from the purchase intention scale. Also, the warmth of the overall country image scale (sizes 1 (sincere) and 2 (trustworthy)), the size of the fascination with

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15 numbered statements (pride) and 16 (admiration) of the statements numbered, the judgment of the product of the scale 5 (reliable) and 6 (good value) of the statements numbered, the animosity, the eco-

conomic scale of 1 (trading) to 5 (unfair trade), 2 (economic power), and 4 (economic influence), and the covariance between the error terms of the correlation of the numbered statements are reviewed.

Table 2. Compliance Values of Scales

	χ^2	df	χ^2/df	GFI	CFI	RMSEA
General Country Image	309,800	96	3,227	0,90	0,95	0,077
Economic Animosity	7,792	3	2,597	0,99	0,99	0,065
Product Quality Judgment	12,173	4	3,043	0,98	0,99	0,074
Purchase Intention	12,259	5	2,452	0,98	0,99	0,062

As seen in Table 2, as a result of the modification, since the compliance values of the measurement models are observed within acceptable limits (Karagöz, 2016), the multifactorial structures of the cognitive and affective dimensions of the country's image and the single-factor structures of the other scales have been confirmed. The reliability of the measurement model was assessed on the basis of consolidated reliability. The CR value of each variable must be greater than 0.7 (Hair vd., 2010, pp. 788). The CR can be explained. All factor loads above 0.70 must have averaged described variance (AVE) values above 0.50 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). To ensure the validity of the merger, the factor burden was based on the 0.50 threshold value proposed by Hair vd. (2010).

As a result of the analysis;

- All variables demonstrated satisfactory reliability, with CR values exceeding 0.70.
- All constructs exhibited good convergent validity, with AVE values exceeding 0.50.
- The measurement model demonstrated acceptable discriminant validity, with AVE values for each construct exceeding the shared variance with other constructs.
- Overall, the results of the reliability and validity assessment indicate that the measurement model is robust and suitable for further analysis.

Cronbach alpha coefficients for factor loads and reliability of scales are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Outcomes of the Measurement Model

Factor	Expression	Factor Load	Cronbach Alph
Economic Animosity	America is not a reliable trading partner.	0,66	0,88
	America wants to gain economic power over Turkey	0,91	
	America is taking advantage of Turkey.	0,91	
	America has too much economic influence in Turkey.	0,68	
	America are doing business unfairly with Turkey.	0,74	
Product Judgement	Products made in America are carefully produced and have fine workmanship	0,87	0,88
	Products made in America show a very high degree of technological advancement.	0,79	
	Products made in America usually show a very clever use of color and design.	0,63	
	Products made in America are usually quite reliable and seem to last the desired length of time.	0,79	
	Products made in America are usually a good value for the money.	0,78	

Contempt	Resentment	0,82	0,93
	Disgust	0,97	
	Contempt	0,79	
	Anger	0,93	
	Hate	0,84	
Admiration	Admiration	0,65	0,83
	Pride	0,64	
	Respect	0,72	
	Fondness	0,88	
Warmth	Well-intention	0,85	0,91
	Trustworthy	0,89	
	Sincere	0,89	
Competence	Efficient	0,76	0,90
	Capable	0,90	
	Confident	0,82	
	Skillful	0,90	
Purchase Intention	I would feel guilty if I bought a American product	0,85	0,90
	I never buy an American product.	0,77	
	I avoid buying American goods as much as I can.	0,89	
	I prefer to buy American goods when appropriate.	0,72	
	I don't like the idea of owning American goods.	0,85	

Findings

Demographic characteristics of the participants

52% of the individuals within the scope of the research

are women, and 48% are men. The median age of respondents between 18 and 33 was 22. 1% are married, and 99% are single. 8% of the respondents have an associate degree, 77% have a bachelor's degree, 10% have a master's degree, and 5% have a doctoral degree.

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Findings

Table 4. Descriptive Data and Correlation Outcomes

	Mean	Standard Deviation	Economic Animosity	Product Quality Judgment	Warmth	Competence	Admiration	Contempt	Purchase Intention
Economic Animosity	3,82	0,96	1						
Product Quality Judgment	3,59	0,89	-,079	1					
Warmth	3,07	1,99	-,456**	,256**	1				
Competence	5,56	2,13	-,079	,497**	,383**	1			

Table 5. Structural Equation Model Coefficients

	Standardize β	Standart Error	Critical Ratio	P	R ²	Hypothesis Testing
H1: Competence --> Economic Animosity	0,08	0,02	1,597	0,110	0,36	Not Supported
H2: Warmth--> Economic Animosity	-0,05	0,04	-,530	0,596		Not Supported
H3: Admiration --> Economic Animosity	-0,26	0,04	-2,549	0,011		Supported
H4: Contempt--> Economic Animosity	-0,38	0,02	-6,191	***		Supported
H5: Competence --> Product Quality Judgement	0,51	0,02	8,622	***	0,30	Supported
H6: Warmth --> Product Quality Judgement	0,05	0,05	,495	0,621		Not Supported
H7: Admiration --> Product Quality Judgement	0,00	0,05	,041	0,967		Not Supported
H8: Contempt --> Product Quality Judgement	0,04	0,02	,788	0,431		Not Supported
H9: Competence --> Purchase Intention	-0,33	0,03	-5,754	***	0,49	Supported
H10: Warmth --> Purchase Intention	0,01	0,05	,187	0,852		Not Supported
H11: Admiration --> Purchase Intention	-0,12	0,05	-1,299	0,194		Not Supported
H12: Contempt --> Purchase Intention	-0,33	0,02	-5,700	***		Supported
H13: Economic Animosity --> Purchase Intention	0,14	0,07	2,529	0,011		Supported
H14: Product Judgement--> Purchase Intention	-0,11	0,06	-2,186	0,029		Supported

Note: * Meaningful p<05, ** Meaningful p<01, ***Meaningful p<001

According to the created model, standardized β coefficients between variables, standard error, critical rate, p and R² values are shown in Table 5.

Admiration economic animosity from the dimensions of the country's image affects ($\beta=-0.26$; $p < .05$); economic animosity to contempt ($\beta=-0.38$; $p < .05$); competence product judgment ($\beta=0.51$; $p < .05$); competence purchase intention ($\beta=-0.33$; $p < .05$); contempt includes purchase intention ($\beta=-0.33$; $p < .05$), economic animosity purchase intention ($\beta=0.14$; $p < .05$), and product quality judgment purchase intention ($\beta=-0,11$; $p < .05$). Thus, hypotheses H3, H4, H5, H9, H12, H13, and H14 of the research have

been supported.

When the R² values of the model are examined, it is seen that 36% of the economic animosity is explained by the affective country image dimensions of the country image, that is, the cognitive country image competence dimension explains admiration and contempt, and 30% of the product quality judgment; 49% of the purchase intention is explained by the cognitive country image competence dimension and the emotional country image contempt dimension, economic animosity and product quality judgment.

Result, Suggestions and Discussion

This study explores the influence of cognitive and affective evaluations of a country and its people on animosity, an inherently emotional concept. By examining the country-of-origin image, the research investigates how a normative concept like consumer animosity affects purchase intentions and how consumers perceive the U.S. from both cognitive and affective perspectives. The study focuses on the interaction between cognitive and affective attitudes and their influence on behavioral intentions.

Animosity is a normative concept; it shows the level at which consumers have social and personal norms about the country of origin, that is, the level of wanting to relate to that country. While buying domestic products is considered appropriate because it supports the domestic economy, consumers can avoid buying products from a country they see as an enemy. Yurcu and Eryiğit (2019) investigated which countries consumers with higher education levels harbor economic animosity towards, and to what extent. They further examined the impact of these hostile feelings on consumers' intentions to purchase products from those countries. The study revealed a negative correlation between consumer animosity and purchase intention, with the strength of this effect varying depending on the intensity of the animosity. Öztürk et al. (2019) investigated the impact of consumer animosity on country image and product evaluation, specifically focusing on the distinction between "easy" and "desirable" goods. Their findings revealed that the human dimension of a country's image influences purchase desire, and that the effects of consumer animosity and country image similarity on product evaluation vary across different product categories. Also, Bayniş and Geçti (2022) explored the influence of consumer ethnocentrism and xenocentrism on consumers' intentions to purchase foreign products. Their research revealed that consumer ethnocentrism, a preference for one's own culture and products, negatively impacts the intention to buy foreign goods. Conversely, consumer xenocentrism, a preference for foreign cultures and products, was found to have a positive effect on the intention to purchase foreign goods.

Although numerous studies have investigated Turkish consumers' feelings of animosity and their impact on purchase intention, no studies reveal the effect of cognitive and affective country image components on animosity feeling, product quality judgment, or purchase intention. Çalık and Gürbüz (2016) examined how the country image between Turkey and Greece affects consumers' intention to purchase products from each other's countries. They concluded that negative emotions such as envy and animosity negatively affect purchase intentions. Özsoy and Altaras (2008) examined Turkish consumers' perceptions of brands from different countries

and how these perceptions affect their purchase intentions. The study shows that consumers' positive or negative perceptions of brand origin can affect their purchase intentions. Dinçer and Dinçer (2014) examined how Turkish consumers' nationalism levels affect their attitudes towards domestic and foreign products and their purchase intentions, and it was observed that consumers with high nationalism levels tended to prefer domestic products. Therefore, research shows that consumers' product reviews are associated with beliefs and feelings towards the countries of origin of the products and the people of those countries.

As a result of the study's analyses, affective country image components (admiration and contempt) affect the feeling of economic animosity. In contrast, the cognitive components (competence and warmth) do not affect the feeling of economic animosity.

It has been found that the perception of competence from cognitive country image components affects product quality judgment; the perceived sense of competence about the people of a country positively affects beliefs about the products of that country. However, the affective country image components do not affect product quality judgment.

Regarding purchase intention, it was found that the competence dimension of the cognitive country image and the affective component of underestimation both play a role. Additionally, economic animosity and product quality judgments (beliefs about the country's products) were shown to influence purchase intention.

This study examines the positive or negative image of the country in their respective international managers, product quality perceptions and to what extent they can influence purchase decisions and can be used to develop effective marketing strategies; it is essential to see how. In this direction, companies should understand the possible adverse reactions of consumers. These negative reactions are sometimes not directly related to the products and services offered by the company but may arise from several socio-psychological reasons, such as country image and animosity. This study finds that the emotional components of country image (admiration and contempt) significantly affect economic animosity. This aligns with prior research by Maher and Carter (2011), which suggested that emotional components might have a stronger impact on consumer attitudes than cognitive components. However, the finding that cognitive components (competence and warmth) do not affect economic animosity contrasts with studies like Cuddy et al. (2007), which typically argue that cognitive components play a significant role in shaping economic attitudes. This discrepancy may be attributed to cultural factors in your sample or differences in methodology.

The impact of animosity affects purchasing beyond

the general beliefs of consumers about imported products purchased. Managers of countries whose military, economic, or political history is disputed must understand how such a macro-level event can affect international marketing activities. This situation will help managers target and select foreign markets. It will allow managers to modify communication and marketing strategies with countries in the regions where there is a feeling of economic animosity, which may exist informally but is a meaningful obstacle to trade (Klein et al. 1998, p. 98).

Managers should understand the importance of the affective and cognitive components of the country's image when deciding on foreign brand strategies to emphasize the country of origin or avoid this emphasis. The research results support past studies, especially the affective dimensions of the country's image, which have been found to play a more dominant role in consumer decisions.

Understanding how another country evaluates a country shows that it has a position in other countries but is also essential in terms of international trade. Companies in countries where warmth and competence are seen as high should emphasize the image of the country of origin because both the affective and cognitive components of the country's image are perceived positively. At the same time, contempt influences consumer decisions in the sense of an unwillingness to buy. On the contrary, companies in countries with low warmth and competence should avoid highlighting the country of origin. Because even though its products are perceived as low quality, negative feelings towards the country also directly affect the purchase intention the products of this country.

As for the countries where animosity is felt, it negatively affects the intention to purchase, regardless of the quality of the products in the relevant country. Countries with high competence but characterized by low warmth and companies facing such conditions should cooperate at the level of governments to improve perceptions of warmth. For example, France has conducted a campaign to convince the French to show a warmer attitude towards tourists (Kotler and Gertner, 2002, p. 48; Maher and Carter, 2011, p. 574).

This study reveals that the cognitive component of country image, particularly competence, positively influences product quality judgment. This is consistent with classic studies by Verlegh (2001) and Bilkey and Nes (1982), which emphasize the importance of cognitive perceptions in product evaluations. However, the lack of a significant effect of emotional components on product quality judgment may diverge from findings in research like Haubl (1996), which suggests that emotional components can influence perceptions of product quality, especially for hedonic products. Also this study indicates that both

competence (cognitive) and contempt (emotional) dimensions affect purchase intention. This supports Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, which highlights the role of attitudes in shaping intentions. However, the finding that other emotional dimensions (such as admiration) do not significantly influence purchase intention contrasts with studies like Lavine et al. (1998), which suggest that emotions can sometimes have a more substantial impact on behavioral intentions. These differences might be due to the demographic characteristics of your sample or the specific product category examined.

Finally, managers should assess the degree of competence of products about citizens of the leading countries of origin, as this is the most meaningful PCI determinant of product country image. Companies in countries with high warmth but low competence have a negative product country image (PCI) due to their low qualification rating. In this sense, for physical products, the relevant country can carry out various image studies that support the image that it is sufficient and capable. Advertisements emphasizing technological development can support the image that a country is talented (Maher and Carter, 2011).

A limitation of the research is that the sample consists solely of young people. This group was selected because young individuals tend to be more open to foreign products, partly due to their opportunities to travel abroad and interact with other countries. However, future research can analyze the differences by examining different demographic groups (Maher and Carter, 2011). Again, the research results cannot be generalized because a particular group was considered. The study's contributions to numerous fields of international marketing, consumer behavior, and brand management are meaningful both theoretically and practically. The following can be used to summarize these contributions: Foreign consumers' perceptions of a nation's goods and services are shaped by its image. Customers can learn valuable information from this image about the dependability and quality of products. A thorough examination of the emotional and cognitive aspects of national image will provide a better understanding of how it influences consumer purchase decisions. While cognitive components (competence and warmth) include more reasoned and informed evaluations, emotional components (admiration and contempt) reflect the impulsive feelings consumers feel toward a nation and its products. An examination of the way these two elements interact will yield crucial information about how marketing strategies ought to be developed. Customers who harbor economic animosity are those who have unfavorable feelings about the prosperity of other nations. Gaining an understanding of how this emotion influences opinions about products and plans to buy will offer strategic insights that help direct brand positioning in

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global marketplaces. Brands may better meet the wants and expectations of their customers by having a deeper understanding of the psychological and sociocultural elements that affect consumers' decision-making processes. As a result, marketing and communication strategies can be created that are more successful.

It is crucial for businesses that operate in international marketplaces to comprehend how consumers behave in various cultural contexts. We will be able to create effective plans and gain a deeper understanding of consumer trends in various markets thanks to this research.

In addition, brands and different product categories can be added in future studies. Future research may also examine the impact of affective dimensions on different categories of hedonic products. Research results should be evaluated with different studies, and the effects of emotion and cognition should be examined.

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